

Analytical and Computational Solutions for Nonlinear Hyperbolic Equation with Inverse Coefficient under Periodic Boundary Conditions

Akbala YERNAZAR^{1,*}, İrem BAĞLAN² and Erman ASLAN³

¹ Department of Mathematics, Akhmet Yassawi University, Turkestan, Kazakhstan, **ORCID:** 0000-0002-0068-4954

² Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, TR-41380, Türkiye, **ORCID:** 0000-0003-4900-6027

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, TR-41380, Türkiye, **ORCID:** 0000-0001-8595-6092

Article Info	Abstract
Oral Presentation Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14288303	This study investigates an inverse problem of unknown time-dependent coefficients in the one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation with periodic boundary conditions. The generalized Fourier method is employed for the analytical solution. To solve the inverse problem numerically Finite Difference Method (FDM) with Gauss Seidel Iteration process is proposed. Two different implicit finite difference schemes are applied, namely, implicit and Crank-Nicolson. A numerical example is presented to illustrate the method's behavior. Both numerical predictions are close to experimental results, however, estimation of implicit scheme has lower true error and relative true error than Crank-Nicolson scheme.
Keywords <i>Finite Difference Method Fourier Method Inverse Coefficient Problem Nonlinear Hyperbolic Equation Non-local Boundary Condition Overdetermination Condition</i>	

1. Introduction

Partial differential equations are considered one of the critical areas of applied mathematics in many fields of science and engineering. In addition, partial differential equations are mainly used in heat transfer in a medium, wave propagation, and dynamics in electric current.

Hyperbolic equations used in wave propagation are also a class of partial differential equations essential in this application. Hyperbolic equations describe how vibrations and especially waves propagate in a medium. Therefore, they are also called wave equations [1, 2].

In the field of engineering, the wave equation plays a pivotal role in understanding and addressing various physical problems and aspects across diverse disciplines. In vibration analysis, the wave equation is employed to characterize the propagation of mechanical waves through structures and systems, aiding in the prediction and mitigation of undesirable oscillations [3]. Heat transfer phenomena, a critical consideration in thermal engineering, are governed by the heat conduction equation, a form of the wave equation, which describes the propagation of thermal waves within materials and systems [4]. In fluid mechanics, the wave equation finds application in the study of acoustic waves and their impact on fluid behavior [5]. Material science researchers utilize wave

equations to investigate the dispersion of electromagnetic waves within novel materials, aiding in the development of advanced optical and electronic devices [6]. Furthermore, system dynamics and control engineers employ wave equations to model and analyze dynamic systems, enabling the design of efficient and stable control strategies [7]. In the realm of robotics, the wave equation finds application in the development of sensors and actuators that rely on wave-based principles for sensing and manipulation [8].

In the present study, we investigate analytically and numerically in the domain $\Omega := \{0 < x < \pi, 0 < t < T\}$, where $T > 0$, an inverse problem of unknown time-dependent coefficients the one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation

$$u_{tt} - u_{xx} = r(t)f(x, t, u), \quad (1)$$

with the initial data

$$u(x, 0) = \phi(x) \quad (2)$$

$$u_t(x, 0) = \psi(x),$$

with periodic boundary conditions

$$u(0, t) = u(\pi, t) \quad (3)$$

$$u_x(0, t) = u_x(\pi, t)$$

and the overdetermination condition

$$E(t) = \int_0^\pi xu(x, t)dx, \quad (4)$$

where ϕ, ψ, E are given functions.

* Corresponding Author: kz.akbala.95@gmail.com

For an analytical solution, the Fourier method is used. For a numerical solution, two different implicit finite schemes which are implicit and Crank-Nicolson are applied.

2. Analytical Solution of the Problem

Definition 1. The problem of finding the pair $\{r(t), u(x, t)\}$ in (1)-(4) will be called an inverse problem.

Definition 2. B is called Banach space when the following set

$$\{u(t)\} = \{u_0(t), u_{ck}(t), u_{sk}(t), k = \overline{1, N}\}$$

of continuous on $[0, T]$ functions satisfying the norm

$$\|u(t)\| = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |u_0(t)| + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |u_{ck}(t)| + \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |u_{sk}(t)| \right).$$

Let's have the following assumptions on the data of problem (1)-(4):

(A1) $E(t) \in C^2[0, T]$, $r(t) \in C[0, T]$.

(A2) $\varphi(x) \in C^1[0, \pi]$, $\psi(x) \in C[0, \pi]$.

(A3) Let the function $f(x, t, u)$ be continuous to all arguments in $\Omega \times (-\infty, \infty)$ and satisfies the following condition

$$\left| \frac{\partial^{(k)} f(x, t, u)}{\partial x^{(k)}} - \frac{\partial^{(k)} f(x, t, \tilde{u})}{\partial x^{(k)}} \right| \leq b(x, t) |u - \tilde{u}|, \quad k = 0, 1, 2,$$

where $b(x, t) \in L_2(D)$, $b(x, t) \geq 0$.

$f(x, t, u) \in C[0, \pi]$, $t \in [0, T]$, $|f(x, t, u)| \leq M$,

$$\int_0^\pi f(x, t, u) dx \neq 0, \quad \forall t \in [0, T].$$

By Fourier Method, we obtain the solution of (1)-(3) as following:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, t) = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\varphi_0 + \psi_0 t + \int_0^t (t - \tau) r(\tau) f_0(\tau) d\tau \right) \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\varphi_{ck} \cos 2kt + \frac{\psi_{ck}}{2k} \sin 2kt \right) \cos 2kx \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{2k} \int_0^t r(\tau) f_{ck}(\tau) \sin 2k(t - \tau) d\tau \right) \cos 2kx \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\varphi_{sk} \cos 2kt + \frac{\psi_{sk}}{2k} \sin 2kt \right) \sin 2kx \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{2k} \int_0^t r(\tau) f_{sk}(\tau) \sin 2k(t - \tau) d\tau \right) \sin 2kx. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Under conditions A1–A3, differentiating (4), we have

$$E''(t) = \int_0^\pi x u_{tt} dx \quad (6)$$

Using equations (5)-(6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} r(t) = & \frac{E''(t)}{\int_0^\pi x f(x, t, u) dx} \\ & - \frac{\pi \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (2k) \left(\varphi_{sk} \cos 2kt + \frac{\psi_{sk}}{2k} \sin 2kt \right)}{\int_0^\pi x f(x, t, u) dx} \\ & + \frac{\pi \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\int_0^t r(\tau) f_{sk}(\tau) \sin 2k(t - \tau) d\tau \right)}{\int_0^\pi x f(x, t, u) dx}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

3. Numerical procedure for the Nonlinear Problem

We develop an iterative algorithm to linearize the problem,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u^{(n)}}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial^2 u^{(n)}}{\partial x^2} + r(t) f(x, t, u^{(n-1)}), \quad (8)$$

$$u^{(n)}(x, 0) = \varphi(x), \quad x \in [0, \pi] \quad (9)$$

$$u_t^{(n)}(x, 0) = \psi(x), \quad x \in [0, \pi]$$

$$u^{(n)}(0, t) = u^{(n)}(\pi, t), \quad t \in [0, T] \quad (10)$$

$$u_x^{(n)}(0, t) = u_x^{(n)}(\pi, t) = 0, \quad t \in [0, T].$$

By setting $u^{(n)}(x, t) = v(x, t)$ and $f(x, t, u^{(n-1)}) = \tilde{f}(x, t)$, we can express the problem (8)-(10) as a linear problem.

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + r(t) \tilde{f}(x, t), \quad (x, t) \in D \quad (11)$$

$$v(x, 0) = \varphi(x), \quad x \in [0, \pi] \quad (12)$$

$$v_t(x, 0) = \psi(x), \quad x \in [0, \pi]$$

$$v(0, t) = v(\pi, t), \quad t \in [0, T] \quad (13)$$

$$v_x(0, t) = v_x(\pi, t) = 0, \quad t \in [0, T].$$

Initially, we employ the linearization method, after that we apply two different implicit finite difference schemes, which are implicit and Crank-Nicolson, for solving (11-13).

Firstly, the implicit scheme is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\Delta t^2} (v_i^{j+2} - 2v_i^{j+1} + v_i^j) = & \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} (v_{i-1}^{j+2} - 2v_i^{j+2} + v_{i+1}^{j+2}) \\ & + r^{j+1} \tilde{f}^{j+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Secondly, the Crank-Nicolson scheme is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\Delta t^2} (v_i^{j+2} - 2v_i^{j+1} + v_i^j) = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{v_{i-1}^{j+2} - 2v_i^{j+2} + v_{i+1}^{j+2}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{v_{i-1}^{j+1} - 2v_i^{j+1} + v_{i+1}^{j+1}}{\Delta x^2} \right) \\ & + r^{j+1} \tilde{f}^{j+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

For time discretization second order backward difference scheme is used, and for space discretization, second order central difference scheme is applied for implicit and Crank-Nicolson scheme.

$$\begin{aligned} v_i^0 &= \varphi_i, \\ v_1^j &= v_{Nx}^j, \\ v_{Nx}^j &= \frac{v_2^j + v_{Nx-1}^j}{2}, \end{aligned}$$

where the computational domain $[0, \pi] \times [0, T]$ is discretized as flows. $x_i = i(\Delta x - 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, Nx$, $t_j = j\Delta t$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, Nt$. Where $\Delta x = \pi/Nx$ and $\Delta t = T/Nt$ are the space in x direction and time steps, respectively. Also, Nx and Ny are two positive integers. $v_i^j = v(x_i, t_j)$, $\varphi_i = \varphi(x_i)$, $\tilde{f}^{j+1} = f(x_i, t_{j+1})$. At time $t = 0$, adjustments should be made in accordance with the initial condition and compatibility requirements. In our numerical computation, $j+2$ exhibits present time, $j+1$ signifies previous of present time, and j denotes previous of previous present time.

In order to determine inverse coefficient $r(t)$, integrating the Eq. (1) with respect to x from 0 to π and using (3) and (4), we obtain

$$r(t) = \frac{E''(t) - \pi v_x(\pi, t)}{\int_0^\pi x \tilde{f}(x, t) dx} \quad (16)$$

The finite difference approximation of (16) is

$$r^{j+1} = \frac{\left((E^{j+1} - 2E^j + E^{j-1}) / \Delta t^2 \right) - \pi (v_{Nx}^{j+1} - v_{Nx-1}^{j+1}) / \Delta x}{(\tilde{fin})^{j+1}},$$

where

$$E^j = E(t_j), (\tilde{fin})^{j+1} = \int_0^\pi x \tilde{f}(x, t_{j+1}) dx.$$

For $j = 0$

$$r^1 = \frac{\left((E^1 - 2E^0 + E^0) / \Delta t^2 \right) - \pi (v_{Nx}^1 - v_{Nx-1}^1) / \Delta x}{(\tilde{fin})^1}.$$

For $j = 1$

$$r^2 = \frac{\left((E^2 - 2E^1 + E^0) / \Delta t^2 \right) - \pi (v_{Nx}^2 - v_{Nx-1}^2) / \Delta x}{(\tilde{fin})^1}.$$

In order to calculate $(\tilde{fin})^{j+1}$, trapezoidal rule for integration is used. The Nx used for numerical solutions is different from the Nin used for trapezoidal rule for integration.

We use Gauss Seidel iteration to compute our implicit (14) and Crank-Nicolson (15) finite difference formulation. Inverse coefficient and source term calculate with using previous present time values. Gauss Seidel iteration formula is given as;

$$v_i^{j+2(s+1)} = \frac{rhs_i}{a_{ii}} - \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} \frac{a_{ik}}{a_{ii}} v_k^{j+2(s+1)} - \sum_{k=i+1}^{Nx} \frac{a_{ik}}{a_{ii}} v_k^{j+2(s)},$$

where s is iteration number. In numerical computations, since time step is very small, we can take $v_i^{j+2(0)} = v_i^{j+1}$. Gauss Seidel iteration for $s = 0$,

$$v_i^{j+2(1)} = \frac{rhs_i}{a_{ii}} - \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} \frac{a_{ik}}{a_{ii}} v_k^{j+2(1)} - \sum_{k=i+1}^{Nx} \frac{a_{ik}}{a_{ii}} v_k^{j+1}.$$

Right hand side terms for implicit finite difference scheme defines as;

$$rhs_i = -2v_i^{j+1} + v_i^j - r^{j+1} \Delta t^2 \tilde{f}^{j+1}.$$

With the same manner, right hand side terms (rhs_i) for Crank-Nicolson finite difference scheme defines as;

$$\begin{aligned} rhs_i &= -2v_i^{j+1} + v_i^j - \frac{\Delta t^2}{2\Delta x^2} (v_{i-1}^{j+1} - 2v_i^{j+1} + v_{i+1}^{j+1}) \\ &\quad - r^{j+1} \Delta t^2 \tilde{f}^{j+1} \end{aligned}$$

and coefficient matrices (a_{ii}) define as with respect to periodic boundary conditions and inner computational nodes. Of course, different coefficient matrices occur for implicit scheme and Crank-Nicolson scheme. Firstly, in every time step, maximum iteration number defines to stop Gauss Seidel iteration. However, for conclude Gauss Seidel iteration in one time step, tolerance value also defines, therefore in some time step size iteration process ends before the maximum iteration numbers. The numerical methods which are described above are implemented in the in-house implicit finite difference code.

4. Numerical Example

If we consider inverse problem (1)-(4) with

$$f(x, t, u) = ue^3 \sin 4x, \varphi(x) = \sin 4x, E(t) = -\frac{\pi}{4} e^t,$$

$$x \in [0, \pi], t \in [0, T].$$

Then the problem becomes

$$u_{tt} - u_{xx} = r(t)ue^3 \sin 4x, x \in [0, \pi], 0 \leq t \leq T,$$

$$u(x, 0) = \sin 4x, u_t(x, 0) = 0,$$

$$u(0, t) = u(\pi, t), u_x(0, t) = u_x(\pi, t),$$

$$\int_0^\pi xu(x, t) dx = -\frac{\pi}{4} e^t.$$

Verifying the analytical solution of this problem is straightforward

$$\{r(t), u(x, t)\} = \left\{ (6t + 9t^4 + 16), e^3 \sin 4x \right\}.$$

In the numerical solutions, 200 of number of meshes (Nx) are used, therefore our space discretization in x direction is 0.0157. Time step size is 0.005s. Maximum iteration per time step is taken as 100 for Gauss Seidel iteration process. However, tolerance value of Gauss Seidel iteration is kept as 10^{-6} . Within this tolerance values, iteration number is less than maximum iteration per time step for every time step.

Additionally, the N_{in} value is taken as 1000 for calculating accurately integration in Eq. 16.

Figure 1 represents the inverse coefficient distribution with time. Numerical and exact results of inverse coefficient enhance with time.

Figure 1. Exact and numerical solutions of $r(t)$ from 0s to 1s.

Table 1. Exact solution, true error and relative true error of $r(t)$ at specific times for both schemes

t[s]	Exact	True error for implicit	Relative true error for implicit [%]	True error for Crank-Nicolson	Relative true error for Crank-Nicolson [%]
0.1	16.6009	0.0321	0.1938	0.0776	0.4677
0.2	17.2144	0.0095	0.0554	0.1468	0.8530
0.3	17.8729	0.0677	0.3787	0.2238	1.2525
0.4	18.6304	0.1538	0.8259	0.3090	1.6589
0.5	19.5625	0.2368	1.2108	0.4046	2.0683
0.6	20.7664	0.3071	1.4789	0.5115	2.4635
0.7	22.3609	0.3766	1.6844	0.6325	2.8286
0.8	24.4864	0.4790	1.9564	0.7718	3.1519
0.9	27.3049	0.6695	2.4521	0.9366	3.4303
1.0	31.0000	1.0250	3.3064	1.1379	3.6707

Figure 2 shows exact and numerical (implicit and Crank-Nicolson scheme) solutions of the $u(x,t)$ for (a) $t=0.25s$, (b) $t=0.5s$, (c), $0.75s$ and (d) $t=1.0s$. Hyperbolic profiles can be observed for exact and both numerical solutions at given times. With increasing time, depth of

In order to compare exact and numeric solution of inverse coefficient, true error and relative true error can be considered. Table 1 shows the exact solution, true error and relative true error of $r(t)$ at specific times for implicit and Crank-Nicolson schemes. Generally, true error and relative true error enhances with time for both schemes. Implicit scheme produces lower true error and relative true error than Crank-Nicolson schema. Maximum relative true error is observed at 1.0s, 3.3064% and 3.6707 are occurred for implicit and Crank-Nicolson schemes, respectively. Relative true error is less than 4.0% for both schemes, therefore, both numerical results are close to exact results for inverse coefficient.

hyperbolic profiles increases. At a given time, symmetric hyperbolic profiles are produced. Solutions of exact and implicit scheme and Crank-Nicolson scheme are so close each other.

Figure 2. Exact and numerical solutions of $u(x, t)$ for (a) $t=0.25s$, (b) $t=0.5s$, (c) $t=0.75s$ and (d) $t=1.0s$

Figure 3 presents the hyperbolic profiles in all times for solutions of (a) exact and (b) implicit scheme and (c) Crank-Nicolson scheme. The same comments can be done for Figure 2.

With the same manner, in order to compare exact and both numeric (implicit scheme and Crank-Nicolson scheme) computations of $u(x, t)$, correctly, true error and relative true error can be observed, again. Figure 4, represents the true errors and relative true errors of both numerical computations at all times. True errors increase with time, and the maximum true errors are observed at the peak points of hyperbolic

profiles for both numerical computations. The maximum true errors of implicit schema and Crank-Nicolson scheme is neatly 0.04 and 0.06 according to exact solution, For solution of implicit scheme, relative true error is not exceed 1% while in Crank-Nicolson scheme, relative true error is nearly 2%. For both numerical schemes, until 0.7s, maximum relative true error is becoming at the boundaries of solution domain. After 0.7s, the maximum relative true error is observed at the peak points of hyperbolic profiles. In the light of these error, implicit scheme produces more accurate results than Crank-Nicolson scheme.

Figure 3. Exact and numerical solutions of $u(x, t)$ for all times

Table 2 exhibits the maximum true error and maximum relative true error of $u(x, t)$ at specific times for both numerical schemes. Maximum true error generally enhances with time, while maximum relative true error stay constant until time 0.7s, after it looks like bell curve. The maximum relative true error occurs at 0.9s for both numerical computations, and 0.94621 and 1.93535 are observed at implicit scheme and Crank-Nicolson scheme, respectively. Again, one can observe that, implicit scheme produces closer results than Crank-Nicolson scheme.

Figure 4. (a) True error and (b) relative true error for all times

Table 2. Maximum true error and relative maximum true error of $u(x, t)$ at specific times

T [s]	Maximum true error of implicit	Maximum relative true error of implicit	Maximum true error of Crank-Nicolson	Maximum relative true error of Crank-Nicolson
0.1	0.00628	-0.49781	0.01254	-0.99296
0.2	0.00633	-0.49491	0.01258	-0.98479
0.3	0.00644	-0.49309	0.01277	-0.97671
0.4	0.00668	-0.49051	0.01428	-0.96892
0.5	0.00709	-0.48738	0.01832	-0.96098
0.6	0.00984	-0.48382	0.02300	-0.95331
0.7	0.01389	-0.47992	0.02873	-0.94621
0.8	0.01998	0.72989	0.03614	1.46588
0.9	0.02924	0.94621	0.04618	1.93535
1.0	0.04357	0.75754	0.06042	1.49578

5. Conclusions

Analytical and numerical investigation of one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation with periodic

condition is done. This investigation contains an inverse problem of unknown unsteady coefficients. For analytical solution, the generalized Fourier method is utilized to calculate Fourier coefficients. For numerical solution, two different

implicit finite difference schemes, namely, implicit and Crank-Nicolson, with Gauss Seidel iteration process is applied. The major conclusions are listed below;

- Inverse coefficient enhances with time for exact and numerical computations.
- Implicit scheme produces closer results than Crank-Nicolson scheme for inverse coefficients.
- One-dimensional symmetric hyperbolic profiles are produced analytically and numerically. With time increases, the depth of the hyperbolic profiles also enhances.
- The maximum relative true error of Crank-Nicolson scheme (2%) is doubled to implicit scheme (1%), therefore, estimation of implicit scheme is closer than Crank-Nicolson scheme
- The given tolerance value of Gauss-Seidel iterations is sufficient to predict hyperbolic profiles for both numerical schemes.

References

- [1] Epstein, B. (1962). *Partial Differential Equations*, 1th ed. McGraw-Hill Book Company Inc.: New York.
- [2] Strauss, W.A. (2008). *Partial Differential Equations*. 2th ed. Wiley: United States of America.
- [3] Marazzani, J., Cavalagli, N., Gusella, V. (2021). Elastic Properties Estimation of Masonry Walls through the Propagation of Elastic Waves: An Experimental Investigation. *Appl. Sci.*, 11, 9091. doi: 10.3390/app11199091
- [4] Tzou, D.Y. (1991). The Resonance Phenomenun in Thermal Waves. *Int. J. Engng Sci.*, 29, 1167-1177. doi: 10.1016/0020-7225(91)01119-N
- [5] Kinsler, L.E., Frey, A.R., Coppens, A.B., Sanders, J.V. (2000). *Fundamentals of Acoustics*. 4th ed.; Wiley: Weinheim.
- [6] Smith, W.J. (2001). *Modern Optical Engineering*. 3rd ed. McGraw-Hill: New York.
- [7] Karnoop, D.C., Margolid, D.L., Rosenberg, R.C. (2012). *System Dynamics: Modeling, Simulation, and control of Mechatronic Systems*. 5th ed. Wiley: New Jersey.
- [8] Hamidaoui, M., Shao, C., Haouassi, S. A. (2020). PD-type Iterative Learning Control Algorithm for one-dimensional Linear Wave Equation. *Int. J Control Autom. Syst.*, 18, 1045-1052. doi: 10.1007/s12555-019-0094-5